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Gender gap in the ownership and use of cryptocurrencies: Empirical evidence from Spain

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ABSTRACT

Over the last few years, the holding and use of cryptocurrencies, as well as the entire ecosystem of decentralised finance (DeFi), has become popular worldwide. However, their acceptance and use are not equal for various reasons; and it is important to know these limiting reasons. There is a gender gap in the acceptance and use of so-called decentralised finance (DeFi), where females have much lower acceptance and usage rates than men. Our study has focused on analysing why this situation occurs. A structured questionnaire was used, including age, level of education and gender, as well as closed-ended questions and questions with respondent ratings (Likert scale). Replicating the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) model, applied in this case to the study on the use and acceptance of cryptocurrencies by females. This has allowed us to generate a sample of 326 people living in Spain, 168 of whom are females. We obtained as a result that the barriers that limit the acceptance and use of cryptocurrencies by females are several: The lack of investment experience in traditional assets, the general lack of knowledge on the part of females about cryptocurrencies; as well as concepts such as blockchain, how to carry out transactions or what an exchange is and how it works. Also, the fact that cryptocurrencies do not inspire any security in females and risk aversion. In contrast, we found no evidence that females do not accept or use cryptocurrencies due to a lack of trust in traditional money, pressure from social media and influencers, fear of not doing the same as the next guy or speculation, which are mostly present in the motivation of males. Nor do we find that income or lack of digital skills among females are barriers to entry.

1. Introduction

Under the pseudonym Satoshi Nakamoto, a person or group devised in 2008 a decentralized digital currency, based on a payment system without a central bank or single authority. This currency was given the name Bitcoin. Bitcoin became operational in 2009, following a message sent to the cryptocurrency mailing list metzdowd.com and signed by the alias "Satoshi Nakamoto". The title of this message was "Bitcoin P2P e-cash paper" (Nakamoto, 2008). Since then, both the growth of its price and the number of users has been exponential. The price went from USD 1 in February 2011 to a peak of USD 69,000 in November 2021. The number of users, estimated at about 5 million in 2016, will be approximately 220 million in 2021 (Auer et al., 2022). It is also the

cryptocurrency with the largest market capitalization, valued at over USD 300 billion (CoinMarketCap, 2023). After Bitcoin, many other cryptocurrencies appeared, such as Ether, Ripple or Litecoin. Therefore, in the last 15 years, cryptocurrencies have evolved from being a new technology oriented to peer-to-peer payments without supervision of a centralized authority; to become mainly financial assets, which are traded by millions of users worldwide (Corbet et al., 2019; Kyriazis, 2021). There is, therefore, interest in determining the degree of adoption of cryptocurrencies. However, assessing it remains a considerable difficulty. This is because reliable and homogeneous data do not exist, as different methodologies are applied to calculate it (Al-Amri et al., 2019). In some cases, from market sources and surveys, interviews, app downloads or transaction-based estimates. This means that, globally and

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Table 1
Degree of adoption of digital currencies worldwide and in Spain.

Source	Date	Geographical Scope	Degree of Adoption	Comments
Índice de adopción de criptomonedas de Finder (Finder, 2022)	oct-22	World	14%	Globally, ownership stands at 14% in the October 2022 report, down from 15% in the previous report. It has decreased slightly.
		Spain	12%	Indicates: 11% female and 13% male.
(Auer et al., 2022)	nov-22	World (selection of 95 countries)	Variable.	Measures adoption via downloads of cryptocurrency exchange apps, total downloads per 1 million population. Higher adoption in Turkey, Singapore, United States and United Kingdom.
(ING Bank N.V., 2018)	2018	15 countries (Europe, USA and Australia)	9%	Sample of 14,828 people, 1,000 from each country.
		Spain	10%	
(Google Trends, 2022)	2022	World	Variable	Only comparative ranking between countries.
		Spain		33/69
(Henry et al., 2019)	2019	Canada	5%	From 2017 to 2019, adoption increases from 2.9% to
(Financial Conduct	2021	United Kingdom	4.4%	Mostly male (78%), with 70% over 35 years of age and 47% of owners with high incomes.
(Dutch Authority for the Financial Markets (AFM), 2021)	2021	The Netherlands	13%	Often own cryptocurrencies: 18-34 years old: 37%; 35-44 years 28%; 45-54 years 17%; 55 years and older: 6%. Declines with increasing age.
(Bitpanda, 2019)	2018	15 European countries plus Russia and Turkey	variable	Switzerland, Ireland and Turkey (14%). Russia (2%) and Italy and France (3%).
		Spain	7%	
(Roa, 2022) Statista	2021/2022	Several countries in the world	Variable	India (27%), Mexico (12%), China (10%)
		Spain	16%	Young, under 35 years old and mostly men.
(Bitpay, 2022)	jun-22	World	16%	In one year it has gone from 12% to 16%. 23% have held a cryptocurrency in the last 12 months.
(Funcas, 2022)	2022	Spain	5%	Young, studying or working, with a high monthly income and residing in large population centers.
(de Miguel Rato & Palomar	2022	Spain	6.8%	Young, under 35 years old and tends to overestimate knowledge.

Source: Own elaboration.

nationally, there are no accurate data comparable by country and cryptocurrency. [Table 1](#) shows current studies on cryptocurrency adoption.

The US cryptocurrency ownership rate is 10%, lower than the global average of 14%. India leads with 28%, and Germany is at the other end of the scale with 6% ([Finder, 2022](#)). From the second global study, in addition to the adoption metric highlighted in the table, the user profile information is worth noting: By far, the largest group of users, almost 40%, were males under 35. Males between 35 and 54 made up another 25% on average. Less than 35% of all users worldwide are females ([Auer et al., 2022](#)). The Internationale Nederlanden Groep (ING Bank NV) study also reports a 9% adoption rate in its sample of fifteen countries, with Turkey showing the highest adoption rate (18%), followed by Romania (12%) and Poland (11%). The USA has 8% and Australia 7%. The countries with the lowest adoption are Luxembourg (4%), Belgium (5%) and France (6%) ([ING Bank, 2018](#)). According to Google Trends, Slovenia, Nigeria, the Netherlands, Cyprus, and Singapore pay the most attention to the term cryptocurrency, which does not imply that adoption is higher ([Google Trends, 2022](#)). A considerable increase has been noted in Canada ([Henry et al., 2019](#)), as well as in the United Kingdom

[Financial Conduct Authority FCA, 2021](#), where the profile of cryptocurrency users has not changed concerning previous studies: mostly males, over 35 years of age and with a medium-high economic level. The Netherlands has a three times higher adoption rate than the United Kingdom (both studies from the same year), above the study conducted by ING, but below Finder's adoption rate. Finally, the study published by Bitpay shows that 46% of merchants accept cryptocurrency payments, but only 23% say they accept payments via crypto wallets ([Bitpay, 2022](#)). The study conducted by [Paxful Team \(2021\)](#), analyses which countries have the highest adoption of cryptocurrencies in daily operations, leaving aside the idea of speculation and trading, only considering transactions with a value of less than USD 10,000. They reach two main conclusions: in emerging countries, including Kenya, Nigeria, Venezuela and Iran, transactions are carried out to protect savings against currency devaluation, to carry out international financial transactions or to transfer money as a bank. There was a downward trend in cryptocurrency investment from March 2021 in China and the United States, coinciding with the start of the pandemic. In China, this reduction in their use may have been due to the progressive closure of this type of operations in the economy. In the USA, it may be due to a

possible professionalization of the sector. However, authors such as [Auer and Tercero-Lucas \(2022\)](#) indicate that its use is predominantly due to speculation. Concerning Spain, the behaviour could be analogous to the situation described at the global level. There is great interest in determining the degree of penetration and adoption of cryptocurrencies, but the studies' results are disparate due to the use of different methodologies. This is due to the potential effects that such adoption may have on monetary sovereignty, macro and microeconomic policies, the financial system, financial inclusion, consumers, and society as a whole ([Náñez Alonso et al., 2020a, 2020b](#)). [Table 1](#) provides information on the most recent studies on the adoption of cryptocurrencies worldwide and also in Spain. As we can see, the degree of penetration and adoption of cryptocurrencies in the Spanish population varies greatly, depending on the study. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out this study, especially focusing on the gender gap. The studies that place the adoption of cryptocurrencies in Spain with the highest degree of penetration are those of [Roa, 2022](#), 16% and [Finder, 2012](#). In the case of Spain, the report by [ING Bank N.V \(2018\)](#) indicates a 10% adoption rate. According to [Google Trends \(2022\)](#), Spain is in the upper middle (33rd place out of 69 regions or countries). However, studies by ([Bitpanda, 2019](#)) (7%), [De Miguel Rato et al., 2022](#) (6.8%) and [Funcas, 2022](#) (5%) show a lower adoption and penetration of this type of asset among the public. What several of the studies do agree on is a clear user profile: a young person, normally under 35 years of age. It should also be noted that two countries worldwide have declared the Bitcoin cryptocurrency a legal tender. The first is El Salvador ([Gorjón Rivas, 2021](#); [Alvarez et al., 2022](#); [McCall, 2022](#)). In fact, in El Salvador, rather than being legal tender, it could be accepted as forced tender, according to the law. This country has even acquired Bitcoin as a form of financing. The second country is the Central African Republic, which in April 2022 announced a surprise vote on a law to legalise Bitcoin in the country as legal tender ([Odeh, 2022](#)); although many economists indicate that the measure is destined to fail ([L. Taylor, 2022](#)).

The article has provided answers to the following questions, which have been the object of the research: what drives the adoption and ownership of cryptocurrencies? Why is there a gender gap in the adoption and ownership of cryptocurrencies? We analyse the following variables: The profile of the public attracted by cryptocurrencies, why cryptocurrencies are used, Knowledge of individuals who invest in cryptocurrencies, how advertising modifies consumer behaviour, Knowledge of risks in using cryptocurrencies, and Risk profile of individuals who acquire cryptocurrencies. The study has been applied in Spain, given that, as discussed in the introduction, it is one of the countries with a high penetration in the use of cryptocurrencies. As limitations to the study, we can point out the geographical scope, that the study is an x-ray of the situation at a specific moment in time and not a study that shows changes or reasons over time.

The article is structured as follows: after a literature review of the various studies published to date on the adoption of cryptocurrencies and the motives behind it, we develop the methodology section, where we describe the materials used and collected as a sample. In turn, in the methodology itself, we replicate the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) model and focus on the responses, motives and results obtained in general (men and women) and in the results obtained by females only we can detect why the gender gap in the adoption and use of cryptocurrencies occurs. We have run the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z statistic that seeks to compare the values of the sample grouped by sex if they follow a normal probability distribution. The parametric test we have used is Student's t-test (Levene's test of equality of variances), while for non-parametric variables, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test has been used. The reliability of the set of questions used in the questionnaire has been measured through Cronbach's alpha. In the results section, we analyse the answers and their statistical interpretation. Finally, the article concludes with a discussion of results, comparing our results with other studies and a series of conclusions.

2. Literature review

Regarding the profile of cryptocurrency investors, if we look at gender, the research shows that investments are mostly concentrated in males ([Faverio and Massarat, 2022](#); [Perrin, 2021](#)). In fact, according to their studies, males are more than twice as likely to have used cryptocurrencies, 22%, compared to 10% of females. [McMorrow and Esfahani \(2021\)](#) indicate a greater use by men than women. [Bohr and Bashir \(2014\)](#), who analysed a sample of 1193 people in 2013 and concluded that males were the majority of users. [Grayscale \(2021\)](#) provides data in line with the same trend observed in previous studies. The gender with the greatest interest in cryptocurrencies continues to be men, 65%, compared to 53% of women. Authors such as [Auer and Tercero-Lucas \(2022\)](#) in their study applied to the US indicate that there is clearly a gender gap in cryptocurrency investment, with males predominating over females. Also, [Jora and Nandal \(2020\)](#) conducted a study in India with 50 participants showing a gender gap as women were less willing to use cryptocurrencies than males. In the case of Turkey [Senkardes and Akadur \(2021\)](#), only 32.6% of females invest in cryptocurrencies, while [Tekler et al. \(2023\)](#) concludes that risk aversion causes this gap. Furthermore, [Bouri et al. \(2019\)](#) indicates that "*crypto-investors mimic the investment decisions of others*", but this effect is smaller in the case of females. In the case of China and Australia, [Xi et al. \(2020\)](#) conclude that gender significantly influences the decision to purchase and own cryptocurrency, with males being more likely than females. In Slovakia, [Vejačka and Pařová \(2019\)](#) detect that females use cryptocurrencies less than males and propose as a solution the digital and financial literacy of women to close this gap. Also, [Sudzina et al. \(2021\)](#) find in their study that males are three times more likely to be buyers and users of cryptocurrencies than females. In Russia, ([Gagarina et al., 2019](#)) find that females use cryptocurrencies less than males due to trust. Also, in the Czech Republic [Sudzina and Pavlicek \(2019\)](#) find gender as a determinant when owning and investing cryptocurrencies, with males being more likely and females less likely, as in the case of the USA ([Bonaparte, 2021](#)) or Germany ([Steinmetz et al., 2021](#)). [Matcu et al. \(2023\)](#) in their study applied in Romania finds that females are more reluctant to invest due to risk aversion and volatility.

[Gemini Trust Company \(2022\)](#) analyses current cryptocurrency holders and potential future buyers. Current investors are males (74%) who invest the most in cryptocurrency, compared to females (26%). But looking at future and potential holders, the situation changes and predicts 53% of females versus 47% of males. Also, in the study reported by [Gemini Trust Company \(2022\)](#), with a sample of 30,000 individuals across 20 countries. In developing countries, females are leading the way in cryptocurrency adoption, which is not the case in developed countries, where more than half of cryptocurrency investments are still made by males. Since Gemini has been conducting the study for several years, it has allowed them to have a whole series of panel data where it can be seen that this gap is tending to close with investments that are increasingly more females than males. Along these lines, ([Henshaw, 2022](#)) concludes in her article that the use of cryptocurrencies by females in the global south, despite existing barriers, would mean greater empowerment and a reduction in financial barriers.

Regarding age [Faverio and Massarat \(2022\)](#) and [Perrin \(2021\)](#) conclude that investments are mostly concentrated in the 18–29-year-old male age group, with 43% of all participants in their study, followed by 30–49-year-old males, with 30%. The study reported by [Gemini Trust Company \(2022\)](#), classifies potential cryptocurrency buyers into the groups: 25–34 (29%), 18–24 (22%) and 35–44 (19%). By age ranges, [Bohr and Bashir \(2014\)](#) analyses a sample of 1193 respondents during 2013, of which 95% were male responses. Responses were concentrated between the ages of 20 and 44, with the distribution becoming more pronounced around the late 20s and early 30s. While it is true that it shows how the accumulation of wealth in Bitcoins grows over the years, in approximate terms, young people aged around 25 have half as many Bitcoins as 35-year-olds, a behaviour repeated for 45-year-olds. These

marginal effects observed cease to have an effect after the age of 45. Grayscale (2021) shows that cryptocurrency adoption levels remain at around 60% from the age of 25–54, after which it drops considerably. Regarding the study by ING Bank N.V (2018), the age range of cryptocurrency investors is very broad, ranging from 18 to over 65 years old. Gemini Trust Company (2022) shows an x-ray of the scenario for both current cryptocurrency holders and potential future buyers. The average age of current investors is 38, while for potential investors, the situation changes, with the average age rising to 44. An interesting point of view is presented by Torosian (2020), who emphasises the importance of Generation Z as drivers of investment in digital assets. Some 20% of Generation Z (born between 1981 and 1996) had invested in cryptoassets, compared to the overall average of 3%. Meanwhile Jora and Nandal (2020), indicate that in India the adoption and use of cryptocurrency is centred in the 18–25 age range and above the age of 45. In the case of China and Australia, Xi et al. (2020) indicate that the greatest preference for investment in this type of asset is among young adults. Sudzina et al. (2021) in their study detect that those who are most likely to operate with cryptocurrencies are also young adults. The same result was reached in Russia (Gagarina et al., 2019). In the US, according to Bonaparte (2021), the majority of cryptocurrency investors are millennials.

Another factor considered by several studies in the adoption of cryptocurrencies is the degree of knowledge or lack of knowledge (Shahzad et al., 2018). Thus, according to ING Bank N.V (2018) men (77%) know more about cryptocurrencies than women (55%). Senkardes and Akadur (2021) in the case of Turkey, they reach the same conclusion as 64% of men claim to know about cryptocurrencies, while 60% of women claim the same. In the case of Poland, (Król and Zdonek, 2022) finds that lack of knowledge about cryptocurrencies is the biggest barrier to their use. In the case of China and Australia, Xi et al. (2020) indicate that cryptocurrency investors say they have a great deal of knowledge of the market and how it works; the same conclusion is reached in the case of Germany by Steinmetz et al. (2021) in their study or also for Austria Stix (2021) when they report that owners, on average, are more financially literate and risk tolerant than non-owners.

More extensive studies also analyse the reasons for choosing to invest or not in cryptocurrencies. First, McMorrow and Esfahani (2021) indicate a higher use by men than women and infer that the reason is a "lack of technological skills". (Almeida and Gonçalves, 2022; Haq et al., 2021) mention how females are more cautious than males when investing, and refrain from investing in areas they consider risky. According to Adhikari and O'Leary (2013) and Adhikari (2017) reach the same conclusion, demonstrating how risk aversion in the case of females is higher than that of males, which could be depriving them of making greater entries into the world of cryptocurrencies. Torosian (2020) states that the reasons for investing in cryptocurrencies are: high rates of return on long-term investments, retirement portfolio, they consider investing for the long term, which allows them to be more relaxed and carefree. Millennials and generation Z are reluctant to traditional assets that were most affected by the 2008 financial crisis. The last reason is that they are clear digital natives, which allows them to be familiar with a world in which they have been moulded. Studies such as the one carried out by Botte and Nigro (2021), speak of the spectacular rise in the price of cryptocurrencies caused by the effect of "joining the trend", doing the same as others or the fear of "being left out". In other words "crypto-investors imitate the investment decisions of others" (Bouri et al., 2019).

In emerging markets, Díaz de León (2021) analyses why people use cryptocurrencies. Because the currency suffers large swings in value daily, they have started to buy cryptocurrencies to protect savings from loss of value. In Russia Gagarina et al. (2019) talks about the lack of trust in the government and the monetary system as a reason for investing in cryptocurrencies. Fuje et al. (2022) report that, despite the exponential growth in the number of cryptocurrency users in Africa, 20% of African countries have banned cryptocurrencies. The reason for their use is to

avoid fluctuations in the value of their currency. In short, some users might seem to distrust their currency or traditional banking and therefore adopt cryptocurrencies. However, studies such as that of Auer and Tercero-Lucas (2022) in the case of the United States or Stix (2021) in Austria, refute this idea, as they clearly show that those who invest in cryptocurrencies do so purely out of speculation. The same conclusion is also reached by Caporal (2021) and Hasso et al. (2019), as the world of cryptocurrencies is still seen as a vehicle for investment and speculation, far from replacing traditional currencies. Jora and Nandal (2020), indicate that in India, the adoption and use of cryptocurrency are the same as in the US to speculate and obtain returns on their investment. In Malaysia Ter Ji-Xi et al. (2021), in Austria Stix (2021) and Mexico López Zambrano and Camberos Castro (2020) find that speculation is the fundamental factor driving the use of cryptocurrencies. In the case of Turkey, again, the speculation motive is indicated in the study by Senkardes and Akadur (2021) and Teker et al. (2023), and they also show two other factors: confidence and volatility in their national currency. This is reinforced in their study conducted in Spain (Gil-Cordero et al., 2020), as trust and knowledge are the factors that most affect investment in cryptocurrencies. Regarding possible ethical concerns derived from the risk assumed when investing in these assets, Jalan and Matkovskyy (2023) carried out a study in three Nordic countries (Denmark, Finland, and Sweden) and concluded that these aspects are put aside thanks to personal trust. The same conclusion is reached by Nurbarani and Soe-priyanto (2022) in the case of Indonesia. Nández Alonso et al. (2021), which indicates that environmental concerns are overlooked when it comes to investing in cryptocurrencies. Neither taxation nor fiscal consequences seem to have an influence, according to Nández Alonso (2019), nor possible fraud, according to Sanz-Bas et al. (2021). Moreover, according to Delfabbro et al. (2021), the behaviour of these risk-loving investors leads them to make decisions that are closer to gambling than to rational investment. Król and Zdonek (2022) or Kumar et al. (2023) show in their study that the lack of funds among young people (generation Z) is not an obstacle to investment but rather a lack of knowledge about cryptocurrencies. Sudzina et al. (2021), Matcu et al. (2023) or Dilanchiev et al. (2023) make an interesting contribution in their study as they show that in the beginning, investors and holders of cryptocurrencies were technology enthusiasts, but now they are mostly speculators, who want to obtain a higher return on their investment. But, above all, they mark an interesting profile: risk-lovers or people with low risk aversion and high self-confidence. In Spain, Arias-Oliva et al. (2019) reinforces the previous statement as being a technology lover explains almost 85% of the intention to use cryptocurrencies, while risk "was not a significant factor". In the case of Malaysia Sukumaran et al. (2022) find that perceived risk did not have a significant influence on cryptocurrency adoption among Malaysian investors. However, in Austria Stix (2021), indicates that high volatility and risk are factors holding back adoption. Meanwhile, in the US Bonaparte (2021) indicates that the reason for investment in cryptocurrencies by millennials is that they have a shorter time horizon than other generations and are more likely to invest in speculative assets (crypto), while other generations with a longer time horizon invest more in productive assets. In Romania Matcu et al. (2023) finds that respondents tended to associate cryptocurrencies with more negative words such as "scam", "fraud" or "loss". However, these perceptions did not dampen their willingness to invest in these assets. Finally, it is interesting to note on investment motives that the cryptocurrency market is strongly influenced by social networks (Ante, 2023; Kyriazis et al., 2022; Ortu et al., 2022). This position is even reinforced in the study by (Gujrati and Uygun, 2020) when they conclude that an individual buys a product after seeing it on a social network 70% of the time. Therefore, influencers and social networks also play a fundamental role in influencing cryptocurrency acquisition behaviour and use. Lammer et al. (2019), shows how investors who hold cryptocurrencies in their portfolios are 3.5 times more likely to hold assets that follow trends than those who do not. Also, such investors prefer truly volatile assets, or in Anglo-Saxon

Fig. 1. Applied Methodology.
 Source: Own elaboration based on (Ajzen, 1991).

parlance, what are known as "lottery stocks". Due to the nature of this type of assets and the excessive risk involved, they could be assimilated to the lottery stocks analysed by Kumar (2009). These assets are always considered to have a low price for their high expected potential, the payoffs are perceived as high risk, and the probability of reward is very small. They are a type of asset rejected by institutional investors but are accepted by individual investors (Kim, 2022).

Income level is another factor that influences the adoption of cryptocurrencies. Thus, Kalda et al. (2021) and Lammer et al. (2019) show that income is a determining factor, as the income of individuals with cryptocurrencies is higher than that of individuals who do not invest. In fact, Lammer et al. (2019) indicates that the income of cryptocurrency investors is higher than that of individuals who do not invest in cryptocurrencies, and they even have higher monthly incomes. In Malaysia, Ter Ji-Xi et al. (2021), find that disposable income fundamentally affects the investment decision. Also, in China and Australia, the study by Xi et al. (2020) shows that the higher the income and the better the social position, the more investment and ownership of cryptocurrencies. In the case of Turkey, Teker et al. (2023) indicates that women prefer to invest between 10% and 25% of their monthly income in financial markets, a much lower figure than men. In the Czech Republic Sudzina and Pavlicek (2019) find income as a determining factor. In the case of Malaysia Sukumaran et al. (2022), there are no significant differences by income

level in terms of cryptocurrency investors. The same result was obtained by Bonaparte (2021) in his study focused on the US or by Matcu et al. (2023) in Romania. (Henshaw, 2022) in her article concludes that the global use of cryptocurrencies by women can help increase financial inclusion and reduce financial barriers.

In short, the review shows that investment is concentrated in young men with a medium or high-income level, who invest for speculation and in the hope of obtaining a higher return; they claim to have a great deal of knowledge about cryptocurrencies. Most studies have focused on motives and profile. And seeing a gender gap in cryptocurrency adoption, we proceed to ask, why is there a gender gap in cryptocurrency adoption and ownership?

3. Materials and Methodology

A structured and defined questionnaire was used to collect data from the sample. The questionnaire included demographic information (age, educational level, and gender), closed-ended questions, and Likert-scale questions in which respondents rated their agreement or disagreement with the statements posed. The questionnaire and the generated dataset are included in the appendix of the manuscript as Annex 1, including a link to the questionnaire. The period of availability to respond to the questionnaire was between July 2022 and January 2023. Following

Fig. 2. Gender distributions of the variables on knowledge, security, purchase and the relationship with money. Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the survey and R V.4.2.3.

Shahzad et al. (2018); Bhuvana and Aithal (2022) and Gunawijaya and Rahadi (2023), who have conducted a literature review of studies on the motives behind investing in cryptocurrencies, we replicated the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) model. The theory of planned behavior postulates that all behaviors are conscious, planned and reasoned. The decision to invest or not in both traditional assets and cryptocurrencies is made consciously and according to objective reasons and with some planning. Therefore, the method is chosen for this study. Applied in this case to the study on women's use and acceptance of cryptocurrencies. This TPB method through computer-based questionnaires has been used by other authors such as Arias-Oliva et al. (2019) or Gil-Cordero et al. (2020) in the case of Spain. In Turkey Teker et al. (2023), in India Jora and Nandal (2020), Poland Król and Zdonek (2022), Czech Republic Sudzina and Pavlicek (2019), Malaysia Sukumaran et al. (2022), Romania Matcu et al. (2023) or Mexico López Zambrano and Camberos Castro (2020). The study has been applied in Spain, given that, as discussed in the introduction, it is one of the countries with a high penetration in the use of cryptocurrencies.

After identifying the factors influencing the adoption, purchase, and use of cryptocurrencies in the literature review, these items were selected and asked in our survey. They are thus included in the measurement of TPB items. After focusing on the responses, motives and results obtained in general (men and women) and the results obtained by women only, we can detect the reason for the gender gap in the adoption and use of cryptocurrencies.

Attitude is an individual's personal evaluation of a behaviour. If the appraisal is positive, the intention is higher. It includes aspects such as behavioural beliefs, beliefs about the likely consequences or other attributes of the behaviour. Here in the case of cryptocurrencies, we can include knowledge/ignorance of the crypto world, previous investment experience, personal confidence, risk (risk-loving/risk-averse), social network influence, advertising/marketing and protection against currency devaluation. Regarding the subjective norm, these are normative beliefs. They are related to the normative expectations of other people, i.e., what the social groups to which the subject belongs expect from him/her. Here we can include the speculation "To the moon", not staying out of the trend "Buy the Dip", risk (risk-loving/risk-

averse) or being a lover of technology. Finally, regarding the perceived behavioural control, it contains the control beliefs. These relate to the presence of factors that may hinder behavioural performance. Here we can include gender, age, income and normative (legal/illegal) regulation.

For the statistical treatment of the data, we have run the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z statistic, which seeks to compare the sample values grouped by gender if they follow a normal probability distribution. Based on these results, we can consider using parametric tests to assess whether the behaviour of men and women can be considered the same or whether there is statistical evidence to differentiate such behaviour according to the sex of the person. The parametric test we have used is Student's t-test (Levene's test for equality of variances), while for the variables mentioned that do not meet the normality requirement, we will use the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test. The reliability of the set of questions used in the questionnaire has been measured through Cronbach's alpha.

4. Results

Table A1 in the appendix shows the survey results according to the gender of the participants in our study. Observing the distributions according to gender, we can see a balance in the percentage of respondents according to this parameter: 48.47% of the participants were males compared to 51.53% who were females. It is assumed that the response rate for females is higher than for males, although it is in this group that we focus our attention. In terms of age, the results for the gender of the participant are repeated. The response rate is higher for women, except for the age groups 18–24, 25–34 and 35–44. That is to say, in the 18–45 age group, the response rate of men is higher than that of women. Regarding educational level, males with high school and/or vocational training are more likely than females. Looking at the employment situation, the percentages in which females outnumber males in the sample are: unemployed, students, students and workers, inactive and retired. Concerning the financial situation of the participating sample there are notable differences between the two genders. Males save more than females, which means that at the end of the month and considering our

Fig. 3. Gender distributions of variables on Exchange, blockchain, transactions, miner, and cryptocurrency phrase. Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the survey and R V.4.2.3.

sample, it is females who use their savings to make ends meet, and lastly, it is worth mentioning that males get into debt more than females. In the variables related to the world of investments, we find that the percentages of affirmative responses of males are higher than those of females in investment funds, I do not count with investments and other; this difference being more accentuated in shares and cryptocurrencies. If we focus on knowledge of the financial system and digital currencies, we can see that females have no knowledge at all, with males predominating in all other areas. About the function of money, we find that men have higher response rates than women in terms of being a means of exchange, and none of the responses are a function of money, with women being more likely than males to be a store of value, a unit of account or a means of exchange, and also a unit of account and a store of value at the same time. As for the security that cryptocurrencies inspire, females bet more than males on no security at all, but also on medium-low security (2–2.5). As to whether they would buy any type of cryptocurrency, females opt for "would never buy it" and also for a medium-low level (2) of risk. Males know better than females how an exchange works, what a blockchain is, how to make transactions with cryptocurrencies, the guarantees that exist when making transactions. As for the reasons why they believe that individuals buy cryptocurrencies, males attribute it more to a lack of confidence in traditional money, the pressure exerted by social networks and influencers, the fear of not doing the same as the person next to them or other reasons such as speculation; while females attribute it more to the fact that it is a safe way to invest or that marketing actions encourage them to do so. Finally, the phrases that females use more often than males when referring to cryptocurrencies are: it is a means of investment or none of the above;

while men prefer it to be a replacement for traditional money, leisure and hobby or that it is a bubble and its value should be zero. .

The knowledge of the financial system and digital currencies can be seen how females respond with lower values than males, with 50% of the responses being between 0 and 2, while in the case of males it varies between 1 and 3. The security that cryptocurrencies inspire has a lower dispersion in females than in males, with the median having the same value in both cases. If you would buy cryptocurrencies according to your level of risk, we find that the dispersion is the same for males and females. However, the measures of central tendency for males are one point higher than for females, with the median for women at one and the median for men at 2, a scale on which 0 is never. .

It can be seen that there are notable differences between males and females in terms of existing knowledge about cryptocurrencies, in the variables referring to the Exchange, blockchain, shares, transactions and digital miners. It is easy to observe how both genders, individuals do not have sufficient knowledge of the concepts referred to, with values that in all cases exceed 50% in negative responses. However, if we look only at the positive responses, there are significant differences between males and females. In percentage terms, males know more than twice as much as females in all the fields asked about. Three cases in particular could be highlighted: "I know how a blockchain works", "I know how to make a transaction with cryptocurrencies" and "I know the figure of the digital miner" where the differences observed between both genders could be considered as "overwhelming". .

As in previous cases, there are notable differences in terms of the reasons that males and females consider that lead individuals to buy cryptocurrencies. It can be seen that females consider more the case of

Fig. 4. Gender distributions of motives for buying cryptocurrencies. Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the survey and R V.4.2.3.

being a safe investment channel and marketing reasons that females think lead individuals to buy cryptocurrencies. In the case of men, we would highlight the case of envy and neighbourliness and not trusting traditional money. In these last two cases, the differences between the two genders would be the most notable. In the case of social networks and influencers, men consider this a more important reason than females, although the differences between the two scenarios are not so significant.

According to the results that can be seen in Table A2 of the appendix (Test Statistics: Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z), we ran the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z statistic that seeks to compare whether the sample values grouped by gender follow a normal probability distribution with 95% confidence. We find that by grouping all the variables according to the gender of the participant, we can indeed consider most of the variables as normal except: "my knowledge about the financial system and digital currencies", "I would buy some type of cryptocurrency according to its risk level", "I know what a blockchain is and how it works", "I know how to make transactions with cryptocurrencies", "I know what a digital miner is and what it is for", "lack of trust in traditional money for individuals to buy cryptocurrencies", "fear of not doing the same as the next guy" and the phrase they would choose to talk about cryptocurrencies are the variables that we cannot consider normal with a 95% confidence level.

Based on these results, we have run parametric tests to assess whether the behaviour of men and females can be considered analogous or whether there is sufficient statistical evidence to differentiate behaviour according to the gender of the person. The parametric test

used is Student's t-test, while the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test will be used for the variables mentioned. The results of both tests are shown in the annex as Table A3 t-test for equality of means and Table A4 Mann-Whitney U non-parametric test.

Concerning the results derived from Table A3 t-test for equality of means, there are differences between the answers given by males and females on the variables: "Their relationship with the investment world focuses on shares", "their relationship with the investment world focuses on investment funds", "I am inspired by security in cryptocurrencies", "I know how an Exchange works and what it is for", "I know what guarantees/security there is when making transactions", "the pressure exerted by social networks and influencers for individuals to buy cryptocurrencies" and other reasons for individuals to buy cryptocurrencies. This result leads us to believe that the predominant responses to these questions are the female group and not the male group.

With regard to the results derived from Table A4, non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test, if we were to focus on analysing whether the results given by females differ from those given by males with 95% confidence, we can affirm the existence of sufficient statistical evidence in the following variables to consider different responses depending on gender: employment situation, financial situation, investment in shares, investment in cryptocurrencies, knowledge about the financial system, security inspired by cryptocurrencies, purchase of cryptocurrencies, knowledge about an Exchange, knowledge about a blockchain, knowledge in transactions with cryptocurrencies, security/guarantees of transactions with cryptocurrencies, knowledge about the digital miner, lack of trust in traditional money to buy cryptocurrencies, pressure

Table A1
Survey results according to participant gender.

Variable	Category	Male		Female	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		158	48.47%	168	51.53%
Age	Less than 18	11	6.96%	17	10.12%
	18–24	53	33.54%	53	31.55%
	25–34	44	27.85%	27	16.07%
	35–44	15	9.49%	12	7.14%
	45–54	13	8.23%	19	11.31%
	55–64	9	5.70%	18	10.71%
	65–74	10	6.33%	13	7.74%
	> 75	3	1.90%	9	5.36%
Level of education	Doesn't Know/Don't Answer	3	1.90%		
	Primary	6	3.80%	11	6.59%
	Secondary	21	13.29%	31	18.56%
	High school and/or vocational training	44	27.85%	38	22.75%
	University and higher education	83	52.53%	87	52.10%
	Others	1	0.63%		
Employment status	Employee, salaried worker	67	42.68%	52	30.95%
	Self-employed, self-employed	13	8.28%	13	7.74%
	Unemployed	6	3.82%	9	5.36%
	Student	41	26.11%	52	30.95%
	Student and worker	11	7.01%	16	9.52%
	Inactive	1	0.64%	2	1.19%
	Retired	10	6.37%	19	11.31%
	Others	8	5.10%	5	2.98%
Financial position	With our current income, we can afford to live an affluent life (we save).	46	29.68%	36	21.95%
	We can live a normal life with our level of income (we save a little).	83	53.55%	87	53.05%
	We make ends meet (we do not save).	19	12.26%	30	18.29%
	We use savings to make ends meet	5	3.23%	10	6.10%
	We get into debt	2	1.29%	1	0.61%
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Investment funds)	No	131	82.91%	147	87.50%
	Yes	27	17.09%	21	12.50%
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Stocks)	No	130	82.28%	156	92.86%
	Yes	28	17.72%	12	7.14%
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Cryptocurrencies)	No	138	87.34%	162	96.43%
	Yes	20	12.66%	6	3.57%
Your relationship with the investment world is centered on: (I do not have investments)	No	95	60.13%	99	58.93%
	Yes	63	39.87%	69	41.07%
His relationship with the investment world focuses on: (I do not have investments, but I am considering investing).	No	131	82.91%	149	88.69%
	Yes	27	17.09%	19	11.31%
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Others)	No	155	98.10%	167	99.40%
	Yes	3	1.90%	1	0.60%
Your relationship with the investment world is focused on: (I do not have investments, but I am informed)	No	157	99.37%	168	100.00%
	Yes	1	0.63%		
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Real Estate)	No	156	98.73%	167	99.40%
	Yes	2	1.27%	1	0.60%
My knowledge of the financial system and digital currencies is 0–5.	No knowledge	22	14.01%	63	37.50%
	0,75	1	0.64%		
	1	42	26.75%	40	23.81%
	1,5	2	1.27%	1	0.60%
	2	40	25.48%	34	20.24%
	2,25			1	0.60%
	2,5			1	0.60%
	3	35	22.29%	22	13.10%
	4	13	8.28%	4	2.38%
	Very high knowledge	2	1.27%	2	1.19%
Check the appropriate box regarding the function of money.	To be a medium of exchange	38	24.52%	33	20.37%
	Value deposit	9	5.81%	14	8.64%
	Unit of account	6	3.87%	1	0.62%
	The above three are a function of money	96	61.94%	108	66.67%
	None of the above is a function of money	6	3.87%	6	3.70%
Cryptocurrencies inspire me with security.	No security	46	29.11%	69	41.32%
	1	42	26.58%	36	21.56%
	2	29	18.35%	32	19.16%
	2,5			2	1.20%
	2,7	1	0.63%	18	10.78%
	3	25	15.82%		
	4	11	6.96%	8	4.79%
	High security	4	2.53%	2	1.20%
I would buy some type of cryptocurrency commensurate with its level of risk.	I would never buy it	32	23.88%	50	41.32%
	1	32	23.88%	25	20.66%
	2	20	14.93%	25	20.66%
	3	17	12.69%	10	8.26%

(continued on next page)

Table A1 (continued)

Variable	Category	Male		Female	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
	4	12	8.96%	8	6.61%
I know how an Exchange works and what it is for	Yes, I would buy it	21	15.67%	3	2.48%
	No	113	71.52%	146	87.43%
I know what blockchain is and how it works.	Yes	45	28.48%	21	12.57%
	No	103	65.61%	150	89.82%
I know how to make transactions with cryptocurrencies.	Yes	54	34.39%	17	10.18%
	No	99	63.06%	148	89.16%
I know what guarantees/security exist when performing these transactions (how are they validated).	Yes	58	36.94%	18	10.84%
	No	111	71.61%	138	83.13%
I know what a digital miner is and what it is used for.	Yes	44	28.39%	28	16.87%
	No	88	56.05%	138	83.13%
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (Lack of confidence in traditional money)?	Yes	69	43.95%	28	16.87%
	No	115	72.78%	151	89.88%
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (pressure exerted by social networks and influencers)?	Yes	43	27.22%	17	10.12%
	No	94	59.49%	119	70.83%
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (Fear of not doing the same as the next guy)?	Yes	64	40.51%	49	29.17%
	No	124	78.48%	158	94.05%
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (It is a safe way to invest)?	Yes	34	21.52%	10	5.95%
	No	131	82.91%	135	80.36%
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (marketing actions drive this).	Yes	27	17.09%	33	19.64%
	No	110	69.62%	106	63.10%
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (Other).	Yes	48	30.38%	62	36.90%
	No	142	89.87%	164	97.62%
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (speculation).	Yes	16	10.13%	4	2.38%
	No	155	98.10	167	99.40%
From his knowledge, if he had to choose one phrase to talk about cryptocurrencies, he would choose:	It is a means of investment	3	1.90	1	0.60%
	The replacement for traditional money	37	27.61	57	47.50%
	Leisure and hobby	34	25.37	20	16.67%
	It is a bubble and its value should be 0.	13	9.70	9	7.50%
	None of the above	42	31.34	24	20.00%
		8	6.0	10	8.33%

Source: Own elaboration based on results obtained from the questionnaire and SPSS.

exerted by social networks and influencers to buy cryptocurrencies, fear of not doing the same as the person next to them to buy cryptocurrencies, another reason to buy cryptocurrencies or the phrase they would use to talk about cryptocurrencies. The reliability of the set of questions used in the questionnaire has been measured through Cronbach's alpha. Table A5 in the appendix shows the results obtained. It can be seen that the reliability of the questionnaire is close to 0.7, reflecting good internal consistency.

5. Discussion of results

There are different studies, such as those by (Bohr and Bashir (2014); Faverio and Massarat, 2022; McMorro and Esfahani, or Perrin, 2021, 2021) that show that investments in cryptocurrencies or their use are mostly concentrated in males. In fact, males are more than twice as likely to have used cryptocurrencies, 22%, compared to 10% of females. In our study, we set out to discover why such a gender gap in cryptocurrency use and adoption exists between males and females.

The study has allowed us to extract several reasons for the gender gap in investment and use of cryptocurrencies. First, when analyzing investment habits, we can observe that males are more willing to invest than females, which is more pronounced in equities and cryptocurrencies. These results align with previous studies, which indicate that cryptocurrency investors tend to have prior experience with traditional assets (ING Bank N.V., 2018; Król and Zdonek, 2022; Senkardes and Akadur, 2021). Therefore, female's lack of prior investment in traditional assets acts as a deterrent to their engagement in cryptocurrency investment.

In terms of knowledge about the financial system and digital currencies, it is observed that females have little knowledge about digital currencies. In fact, females obtain worse results when measuring the degree of knowledge of different issues such as what an exchange is and how it works, what a blockchain is, how to make transactions with cryptocurrencies or the guarantees that exist when making transactions.

This lack of knowledge and training is clearly a major obstacle. Previous studies such as those on Poland (Król and Zdonek, 2022), China and Australia (Xi et al., 2020), Germany (Steinmetz et al., 2021) or Austria (Stix, 2021), speak of this lack of knowledge as a limiting factor in the adoption and use of cryptocurrencies.

Related to the above is the safety factor. It is difficult to think that something is safe when you do not know about it and have no training in it (Sohaib et al., 2020). Thus, as regards the security that cryptocurrencies inspire, females overwhelmingly indicate in the questionnaire conducted that cryptocurrencies do not inspire them any security at all. The minority of females who indicate that cryptocurrencies inspire them some security indicate low security (2 on a scale of 1–5). This reason confirms the results of previous studies such as those of, who mention how females are more cautious than males when it comes to making their investments, and refrain from investing in areas they consider dangerous (Almeida and Gonçalves, 2022; Haq et al., 2021). Also, in the case of Turkey Senkardes and Akadur (2021) or Teker et al. (2023) talk about security and trust or Jalan and Matkovskyy (2023) come to the same conclusion for Denmark, Finland, and Sweden. Therefore, this lack of knowledge about cryptocurrencies and their security results in the question of whether they would buy any type of cryptocurrency, with the majority of females indicating that they would "never buy it".

The aforementioned lack of knowledge and lack of safety therefore affect the level of risk-taking, which makes the females surveyed risk averse, resulting in medium-low risk-taking (2, on a scale of 1–5). This is consistent with the studies conducted by Almeida and Gonçalves (2022) and Haq et al. (2021), where it is mentioned that females are more cautious than males when making their investments; to which Adhikari and O'Leary (2013) and B. K. Adhikari (2017) add that risk aversion in the case of females is higher than that of males, which makes them invest less in cryptocurrency or assume its use. The same position is defended by Gagarina et al. (2019) or Matcu et al. (2023). On the contrary, in the case of males Delfabbro et al. (2021) states that the behaviour of these

Table A2

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z test statistics.

	Maximum extreme differences			Kolmogorov-Smirnov's Z	Sig. asin. (bilateral)
	Absolute	Positive	Negative		
Indicate your age range.	0.130	0.032	-0.130	1.170	0.129
Check the appropriate box in relation to your level of education.	0.062	0.062	-0.019	0.555	0.917
Please indicate your current employment status.	0.123	0.021	-0.123	1.105	0.174
If you had to choose a phrase to define your family's financial situation, which one would you choose?	0.082	0.007	-0.082	0.734	0.654
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Investment funds)	0.046	0.046	0.000	0.414	0.995
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Stocks)	0.106	0.106	0.000	0.955	0.322
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Cryptocurrencies)	0.091	0.091	0.000	0.820	0.512
Your relationship with the investment world is centered on: (I do not have investments)	0.012	0.000	-0.012	0.108	1.000
His relationship with the investment world focuses on: (I do not have investments, but I am considering investing).	0.058	0.058	0.000	0.521	0.949
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Others)	0.013	0.013	0.000	0.118	1.000
His relationship with the investment world is centered on: (I do not have investments, but I am informed.	0.006	0.006	0.000	0.057	1.000
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Real Estate)	0.007	0.007	0.000	0.061	1.000
My knowledge of the financial system and digital currencies is 0-5.	0.235	0.235	0.000	2.116	< 0.001
Check the box that applies to the function of money.	0.046	0.002	-0.046	0.406	0.997
Cryptocurrencies inspire me with security.	0.122	0.122	0.000	1.100	0.178
I would buy some type of cryptocurrency commensurate with its level of risk.	0.200	0.000	-0.200	1.591	0.013
I know how an Exchange works and what it is used for.	0.159	0.159	0.000	1.433	0.033
I know what blockchain is and how it works.	0.242	0.242	0.000	2.178	< 0.001
I know how to make transactions with cryptocurrencies.	0.261	0.261	0.000	2.344	< 0.001
I know what guarantees/security exist when performing these transactions (how are they validated).	0.115	0.115	0.000	1.031	0.238
I know what a digital miner is and what it is used for.	0.271	0.271	0.000	2.433	< 0.001
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (Lack of confidence in traditional money)?	0.171	0.171	0.000	1.543	0.017
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (pressure exerted by social networks and influencers)?	0.113	0.113	0.000	1.023	0.246
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (Fear of not doing the same as the next guy)?	0.156	0.156	0.000	1.405	0.039
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (It is a safe way to invest)?	0.026	0.000	-0.026	0.230	1.000
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (marketing actions drive this).	0.065	0.000	-0.065	0.589	0.879
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (Other).	0.077	0.077	0.000	0.699	0.713
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (speculation).	0.013	0.013	0.000	0.118	1.000
From his knowledge, if he had to choose one phrase to talk about cryptocurrencies, he would choose:	0.199	0.024	-0.199	1.582	0.013

^aGrouping variable: Sex.

Source: Own elaboration based on results obtained from the questionnaire and SPSS.

risk-loving investors leads them to make decisions that are closer to gambling than to rational investment. Also, [Sukumaran et al. \(2022\)](#) find that male's perceived risk had no significant influence on cryptocurrency adoption among Malaysian investors.

On the reasons why they believe individuals buy cryptocurrencies, a fundamental difference between males and females emerges. Men attribute more to it:

1. Lack of trust in traditional money. This is in line with some studies such as those conducted by [Gagarina et al. \(2019\)](#), [Teket et al. \(2023\)](#) or [Gil-Cordero et al. \(2020\)](#), which point to a lack of trust in the government and the monetary system as a reason for investing in cryptocurrencies. However, studies by [Auer and Tercero-Lucas \(2022\)](#) in the case of the United States or [Stix \(2021\)](#) in Austria refute this idea.
2. [Torosian \(2020\)](#) notes that millennials and Generation Z, being digital natives, are more likely to invest in this type of digital asset. It also agrees with [Ante \(2023\)](#); [Kyriazis et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Ortu et al. \(2022\)](#), who indicate that social networks strongly influence investment in the cryptocurrency market. This position is even reinforced in the study by [\(Gujrati and Uygun, 2020\)](#), when they conclude that an individual buys a product after seeing it on a social network 70% of the time.

3. Fear of missing out (FOMO) or fear of not doing the same as the next person. This reason is in line with the studies by [Botte and Nigro \(2021\)](#), the effect of "joining the trend", doing the same as others for fear of being "left out"; or by [Bouri et al. \(2019\)](#) "crypto-investors imitate the investment decisions of others", although this effect in females is lower. Companies from all economic sectors, through marketing campaigns and by using influencers in many cases, are looking for new ways to connect with consumers; "cryptofriendly" being one of them. The goal is clear: to influence the consumer to accept their cryptofriendly products, which in turn will guarantee them greater social acceptance by being "innovative" or "embracing the trend". However, consumers currently perceive these actions with a certain indifference ([García-Estévez, 2022](#)).
4. Speculation. This result is consistent with studies such as those of [Sudzina et al. \(2021\)](#), [Matcu et al. \(2023\)](#), [Dilanchiev et al. \(2023\)](#) or [Nguyen et al. \(2023\)](#) who indicate that they are mostly speculators who want to get a higher return on their investment.

Finally, the phrase to talk about cryptocurrencies that females bet more on than males are: it is a means of investment, none of the above, or that it is a bubble and its value should be 0, while men bet on it as a replacement for traditional money, leisure and hobby.

In our study, we have not found the findings of [McMorrow and Esfahani \(2021\)](#), who indicate a higher use by males than females, and

Table A3
Tt-test for equality of means.

Levene's test of equality of variances		t-test for equality of means								
F	Sig.	t	gl	Significance		Difference in averages	Standard error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference		
				P of a factor	Two-factor P			Inferior	Superior	
15.954	0.000	-1.763	324	0.039	0.079	-0.375	0.213	-0.793	0.043	
		-1.773	318.696	0.039	0.077	-0.375	0.211	-0.791	0.041	
0.546	0.460	0.638	323	0.262	0.524	0.069	0.107	-0.143	0.280	
		0.638	321.928	0.262	0.524	0.069	0.107	-0.143	0.280	
0.468	0.494	-1.877	323	0.031	0.061	-0.447	0.238	-0.915	0.022	
		-1.875	320.351	0.031	0.062	-0.447	0.238	-0.916	0.022	
0.425	0.515	-1.891	317	0.030	0.060	-0.175	0.092	-0.356	0.007	
		-1.892	316.637	0.030	0.059	-0.175	0.092	-0.356	0.007	
5.498	0.020	1.167	324	0.122	0.244	0.046	0.039	-0.031	0.123	
		1.163	312.725	0.123	0.246	0.046	0.039	-0.032	0.124	
37.479	0.000	2.939	324	0.002	0.004	0.106	0.036	0.035	0.177	
		2.905	273.048	0.002	0.004	0.106	0.036	0.034	0.177	
41.505	0.000	3.061	324	0.001	0.002	0.091	0.030	0.032	0.149	
		3.012	242.839	0.001	0.003	0.091	0.030	0.031	0.150	
0.193	0.661	-0.220	324	0.413	0.826	-0.012	0.055	-0.119	0.095	
		-0.220	322.950	0.413	0.826	-0.012	0.055	-0.119	0.095	
9.130	0.003	1.498	324	0.067	0.135	0.058	0.039	-0.018	0.134	
		1.491	307.482	0.069	0.137	0.058	0.039	-0.018	0.134	
4.614	0.032	1.067	324	0.143	0.287	0.013	0.012	-0.011	0.037	
		1.050	244.291	0.147	0.295	0.013	0.012	-0.011	0.037	
4.309	0.039	1.031	324	0.152	0.303	0.006	0.006	-0.006	0.018	
		1.000	157.000	0.159	0.319	0.006	0.006	-0.006	0.019	
1.606	0.206	0.632	324	0.264	0.528	0.007	0.011	-0.014	0.028	
		0.625	276.385	0.266	0.532	0.007	0.011	-0.014	0.028	
0.898	0.344	-0.666	315	0.253	0.506	-0.099	0.148	-0.389	0.192	
		-0.666	312.802	0.253	0.506	-0.099	0.148	-0.390	0.193	
1.342	0.248	2.210	323	0.014	0.028	0.32615	0.14758	0.03582	0.61649	
		2.206	318.286	0.014	0.028	0.32615	0.14785	0.03527	0.61704	
56.753	0.000	3.623	323	0.000	0.000	0.159	0.044	0.073	0.245	
		3.593	287.372	0.000	0.000	0.159	0.044	0.072	0.246	
25.252	0.000	2.489	319	0.007	0.013	0.115	0.046	0.024	0.206	
		2.473	300.047	0.007	0.014	0.115	0.047	0.024	0.207	
16.868	0.000	2.159	324	0.016	0.032	0.113	0.053	0.010	0.217	
		2.154	317.913	0.016	0.032	0.113	0.053	0.010	0.217	
1.415	0.235	-0.593	324	0.277	0.553	-0.026	0.043	-0.110	0.059	
		-0.594	323.981	0.276	0.553	-0.026	0.043	-0.110	0.059	
6.142	0.014	-1.244	324	0.107	0.214	-0.065	0.052	-0.168	0.038	
		-1.246	323.939	0.107	0.214	-0.065	0.052	-0.168	0.038	
38.200	0.000	2.942	324	0.002	0.003	0.077	0.026	0.026	0.129	
		2.889	229.027	0.002	0.004	0.077	0.027	0.025	0.130	
4.614	0.032	1.067	324	0.143	0.287	0.013	0.012	-0.011	0.037	
		1.050	244.291	0.147	0.295	0.013	0.012	-0.011	0.037	

Source: Own elaboration based on results obtained from the questionnaire and SPSS.

infer that the reason is "lack of technological skills". Although it is possible that, as the sample is concentrated on Spain, a developed country, there is no barrier effect due to a lack of digital skills. Nor has evidence been found that females invest less in cryptocurrencies because of their income level, as previous studies such as those by (Kalda et al., 2021) or (Lammer et al., 2019) have argued. At the same time, there is also no evidence such as that collected by Tjondro et al. (2023), who found investment in cryptocurrencies due to their desire to be accepted in the social group and influencers in the group of females.

Educational measures should therefore be taken to raise awareness of the uses and risks of cryptocurrencies, especially among the female population. This is likely to increase adoption and use. One example would be the path initiated by the Bahamas with its CBDC training program at country level, whose main objective is to "accelerate education around digital financial services" (Central Bank of the Bahamas, 2023). Another option would be to implement training and education plans in digital finance at the regional level (Apostu et al., 2022). Even at the local level, especially with the groups that have more difficulties with digital finance by residing in rural areas where the technological gap is greater (Náñez Alonso et al., 2020a, 2020b; Náñez Alonso et al., 2022); and especially focused on lower income and education groups,

who usually have more difficulties with the digitization of finances (Gómez-Fernández and Albert, 2019). Furthermore, according to (Henshaw, 2022), the use of cryptocurrencies by females in underdeveloped countries can help increase financial inclusion and reduce financial barriers (Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2017). Financial inclusion is considered to be an element that facilitates the achievement of seven of the seventeen Sustainable Development Goals, but especially Goal 8, which seeks to Strengthen the capacity of domestic financial institutions to promote and expand access to banking, financial and insurance services for all (Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2017). Increasing citizens' interest in financial technology (FinTech) and information about CBDC and cryptocurrencies are positive determinants for increasing financial inclusion (Ozili, 2023). Fintech, CBDCs and cryptocurrency can increase financial inclusion by providing an alternative channel through which unbanked adults can access formal financial services (Ozili, 2022).

The number of responses obtained was 326 (n = 326), valid responses considering previously validated studies. Thus, our study would have a higher number of responses than the cases of Turkey Teker et al. (2023) 288 respondents; India Jora and Nandal (2020) 50 respondents; the Czech Republic Sudzina and Pavlicek (2019) with 62; Malaysia Ter Ji-Xi et al. (2021) 290 respondents; Australia and China Xi et al. (2020)

Table A4
Non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test.

	Mann-Whitney U	W for Wilcoxon	Z	Sig. asin. (bilateral)
Indicate your age range.	12407.000	24968.000	-1.042	0.297
Check the appropriate box in relation to your level of education.	12695.000	26723.000	-0.643	0.520
Please indicate your current employment status.	11495.500	23898.500	-2.078	0.038
If you had to choose a phrase to define your family's financial situation, which one would you choose?	11165.500	23255.500	-2.062	0.039
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Investment funds)	12663.000	26859.000	-1.167	0.243
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Stocks)	11868.000	26064.000	-2.905	0.004
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Cryptocurrencies)	12066.000	26262.000	-3.022	0.003
Your relationship with the investment world is centered on: (I do not have investments)	13113.000	25674.000	-0.220	0.826
His relationship with the investment world focuses on: (I do not have investments, but I am considering investing).	12505.000	26701.000	-1.496	0.135
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Others)	13099.000	27295.000	-1.067	0.286
His relationship with the investment world is centered on: (I do not have investments, but I am informed.	13188.000	27384.000	-1.031	0.302
Its relationship with the investment world is focused on: (Real Estate)	13183.000	27379.000	-0.633	0.527
My knowledge of the financial system and digital currencies is 0–5.	9336.000	23532.000	-4.672	0.000
Check the box that applies to the function of money.	12018.000	24108.000	-0.775	0.438
Cryptocurrencies inspire me with security.	11362.000	25390.000	-2.239	0.025
I would buy some type of cryptocurrency commensurate with its level of risk.	6001.500	13382.500	-3.678	0.000
I know how an Exchange works and what it is used for.	11094.500	25122.500	-3.557	0.000
I know what blockchain is and how it works.	9935.000	23963.000	-5.258	0.000
I know how to make transactions with cryptocurrencies.	9630.000	23491.000	-5.518	0.000
I know what guarantees/ security exist when performing these transactions (how are they validated).	11383.000	25244.000	-2.469	0.014
I know what a digital miner is and what it is used for.	9502.000	23363.000	-5.299	0.000

Table A4 (continued)

	Mann-Whitney U	W for Wilcoxon	Z	Sig. asin. (bilateral)
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (Lack of confidence in traditional money)?	11003.000	25199.000	-3.975	0.000
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (pressure exerted by social networks and influencers)?	11767.000	25963.000	-2.147	0.032
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (Fear of not doing the same as the next guy)?	11206.000	25402.000	-4.105	0.000
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (It is a safe way to invest)?	12933.000	25494.000	-0.594	0.553
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (marketing actions drive this).	12406.000	24967.000	-1.243	0.214
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (Other).	12244.000	26440.000	-2.908	0.004
For which of the following reasons do you consider that individuals buy cryptocurrencies (speculation).	13099.000	27295.000	-1.067	0.286
From his knowledge, if he had to choose one phrase to talk about cryptocurrencies, he would choose:	6652.000	13912.000	-2.474	0.013

^aGrouping variable: Sex.

Source: Own elaboration based on results obtained from the questionnaire and SPSS.

Table A5
Reliability analysis - Cronbach's alpha.

Cronbach's alpha	Cronbach's alpha based on standardized items	Number of items
0.677	0.738	24

Source: Own elaboration based on results obtained from the questionnaire and SPSS.

250 respondents; Russia [Gagarina et al. \(2019\)](#) 262 respondents; Malaysia [Sukumaran et al. \(2022\)](#) 211 respondents, Romania [Matcu et al. \(2023\)](#) with 98 respondents, Georgia [Dilanchiev et al. \(2023\)](#) with 175 respondents or in Mexico [López Zambrano and Camberos Castro \(2020\)](#) with 106 respondents. Our study would have a similar number of respondents to other studies, such as those in Turkey [Senkardes and Akadur \(2021\)](#) 399 respondents; China [Shahzad et al. \(2018\)](#) 376 respondents; Poland [Król and Zdonek \(2022\)](#) 398 respondents; Indonesia [Nurbarani and Soepriyanto \(2022\)](#) 400 respondents; Spain [Arias-Oliva et al. \(2019\)](#) 402 respondents, age 20 years only. Also, in Spain [Gil-Cordero et al. \(2020\)](#) with a sample of 327 respondents. Our

study with 326 respondents would be below other studies, such as the one executed in the Nordic countries by [Jalan and Matkovskyy \(2023\)](#) with 500 respondents in Denmark, 518 in Finland, or 501 in Sweden; or in the case of Slovakia [Vejačka & Pařov \(2019\)](#) where 616 respondents participated.

Although numerous studies, both by public and private organisations and by academics and researchers, analyse the degree of adoption of cryptocurrencies and the variables or factors that influence it, one issue has not been addressed in depth. One issue that has not been addressed in depth is why is there a gender gap in the adoption and ownership of cryptocurrencies? Most studies have focused on finding or analysing the variables that determine the use of cryptocurrencies, such as income, age, gender, confidence, level of education, and others. But the reverse question has not been asked. That is, if it has been found that females participate less in the cryptocurrency market and own less cryptocurrencies, why is this the case? In our study, we have focused on this situation to close an academic gap and determine why females are participating less in decentralised finance. As limitations to the study, we can point out that as it was carried out in a developed country such as Spain, which is part of a stable monetary system such as the Eurozone, some of the reasons that generate the gender gap, such as the lack of digital skills or the distrust and volatility of the national currency, are not being addressed. It is important to note that [Paxful Team \(2021\)](#) in emerging countries, including Kenya, Nigeria, Venezuela and Iran, transactions are carried out to protect savings against currency devaluation, to carry out international financial transactions or to transfer money as a bank. Another limitation of the study is that it is an x-ray of the situation at a specific moment and not a study that shows changes or reasons over time. To overcome this, as a line of research in the future, it is proposed to measure this situation again to analyse the evolution over time of the gap in the use and adoption of cryptocurrencies by females.

6. Conclusions

There is undoubtedly a gender gap in the acceptance and use of so-called decentralised finance (DeFi) today, where women have much lower acceptance rates than men. In our study we have focused on analysing why this situation arises.

The results of the study are based on 326 responses from people living in Spain, of which 168 are females. This circumstance may limit the generalizability of the conclusions to a wider population. We found that the reasons for this gender gap are:

Firstly, the lack of investment experience in traditional assets is an initial barrier to entry for women in the use and holding of cryptocurrencies.

Secondly, females's general lack of knowledge about cryptocurrencies, not only about cryptocurrencies but also about concepts such as blockchain, how to make transactions, what an exchange is, and how it works. All of this represents a second major barrier for females in using and holding cryptocurrencies.

Thirdly, females overwhelmingly indicate that cryptocurrencies do not inspire them with any sense of security. Therefore, this lack of knowledge about cryptocurrencies and lack of security results in most women suggesting that they would "never buy" any type of cryptocurrency when asked whether they would buy it. This lack of knowledge and security, therefore, also affects the level of risk-taking, which leads the females surveyed to show risk aversion, resulting in medium-low risk-taking (2). They are more cautious than men when making their investments. Women's risk aversion is higher than men's, which leads them to invest less in cryptocurrencies or assume their use. This risk aversion is therefore presented as the fourth barrier.

In turn, females (unlike males) are not motivated to invest or use cryptocurrencies due to a lack of trust in traditional money. The results also show that the pressure exerted by social networks and influencers has less effect on women than on men when it comes to investing. Similar results are obtained with the motive of fear of not doing the same

as the person next to them or speculation, the latter reason being in line with what has been argued concerning risk aversion.

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Conceptualization, Sergio Luis Nández Alonso; Methodology, Sergio Luis Nández Alonso.; Software, Beatriz María Sastre Hernández y Pablo Arroyo Rodríguez.; validation, Javier Jorge Vázquez and Sergio Luis Nández Alonso; Formal analysis, Sergio Luis Nández Alonso and Beatriz María Sastre Hernández; Investigation, Pablo Arroyo Rodríguez, Sergio Luis Nández Alonso and Javier Jorge Vázquez; Resources, Javier Jorge Vázquez and Pablo Arroyo Rodríguez; Data curation, Pablo Arroyo Rodríguez and Beatriz María Sastre Hernández; Writing – original draft preparation, Sergio Luis Nández Alonso, Beatriz María Sastre Hernández and Pablo Arroyo Rodríguez.; Writing – review & editing, Javier Jorge Vázquez; Supervision, Sergio Luis Nández Alonso; Funding, Sergio Luis Nández Alonso, Javier Jorge Vázquez and Beatriz María Sastre Hernández. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Institutional Review Board Statement

No applicable. The survey was carried out in such a way as to guarantee the anonymity of the participating subjects. All participants were informed of the purpose of the survey. In turn, their consent was obtained digitally, before starting the questionnaire, indicating that they wished to participate in the study.

Annex 1

Link to questionnaire and Dataset:
<https://portalcientifico.ucavila.es/datos/64a67b68418689090e7f1462>.

Annex 2. Statistics

See [Tables A1-A5](#) here.

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